

Training needs analysis of the teachers in a university in Cavite, Philippines

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Abstract

Training needs analysis (TNA) is essential to determine the gap between employees' training and their needs. Thus, it can help the researchers to identify the attitudes, skills, and concepts that have been acquired by the professionals, particularly in the teachers. A descriptive study was conducted with thirty-seven (37) faculty members of University of Perpetual Help Molino Campus in Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines as respondents of the study. A survey questionnaire is created to determine the functional competencies of the teachers. This result shows that the areas of Research Skills, Effective Writing, Syllabus Development, and Student Evaluation have been improved by most of the teachers. The other seven competencies such as Marketing Skills, Community Outreach, Classroom Management, Subject Matter Expertise, Instructional Materials Development, Effective Instructional Delivery, and Technology Competency should also be given equal attention and consideration. It implies that these competencies must be addressed immediately to enhance the skills needed by the faculty members in this college. The study suggested that a professional development activity framework (PDAF) combined with school-based faculty development programs (SB-FDP) must be initiated and implemented in the university encompassing the 11 identified functional competencies of the teachers.

Keywords: Training needs analysis; teachers; university; Philippines.

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Introduction

The workforce or employees are the greatest resources that an institution of higher learning could ever have. Despite the tremendous influence that the digital age brought about, the quality of employees and the training they have received or will receive impact the delivery of services to students, alumni, parents, and other stakeholders. Hence, they constitute the lifeblood of an agency or organization, and no modern instrument nor gadget in this modern time could ever replace the significance of well-trained employees both at micro and macro levels in carrying out the operations of any organization (Bamberg et al., 2021; Dahiya & Jha, 2011; Vatanartiran & Karadeniz, 2015).

Human resource management is a vital component in the quality operation of an institution of higher learning (Abomaradan et al., 2020). The workforce is by far the most significant of all resources because no institution can move forward without the presence of the efficacious workers who willingly perform their respective job towards the achievement and fulfillment of the philosophy, mission, vision, quality policy, and objectives of University of Perpetual Help Molino Campus in Cavite, Philippines.

Absolutely, the analysis of training needs often focuses on work performance. People realize a training requirement if they are unable to properly complete the many tasks that make up their occupations or if another issue, such as equipment failure or dissatisfaction restricts performance. Employees focus on job performance because it can be observed and because it aligns with the behaviorist learning model, which dominates most discussions of training. In the current context, where the nature of occupations and competencies are susceptible to ongoing change, it might be made that this approach is no longer acceptable (Anderson, 1994). Gould et al. (2004) added that the first step in a cycle that influences the general training and educational plan of staff members in an organization of professionals is the study of training needs. The cycle starts with a thorough consultation to determine the population under consideration's learning needs, then moves on to course preparation, delivery, and evaluation.

Related studies were conducted to determine the effectiveness of training needs analysis among teachers. Czerniawski et al. (2017) provided a study on the professional developmental needs of higher education-based teacher educators by which teachers are passionate to learn with and from their colleagues and peers, but a lack of support was discovered among teachers in different countries. In a study by Chin et al. (2022), results showed that activities particularly in the teacher professional development have a positive impact in classroom settings, however teachers still need to enhance some of the skills they can integrate in the teaching-learning process such as the utilization of information and communication technologies (ICTs), online teaching strategies, and research development. Another study by Liwanag et al. (2023) said that most of the teachers have acquired the functional and research competencies for their academic and practical fields, although some competencies such as effective instructional delivery, effective writing, and research skills were very low.

Given the premises, it is the direction of the study to determine the actual and work-related trainings that the faculty members of the College of Arts and Sciences and College of Education need for them to deliberately discharge their teaching responsibilities to the students that lead to their satisfaction and holistic development as members of the university upon which their academic training is entrusted to their teachers with the unconditional support from the top management. Moreover, it will help other people to be more proactive and productive employees now and in the years to come as they continue to serve the needs of this university.

Methodology

Descriptive research study was utilized of which description is the primary goal instead of focusing on interactions or associations. Additionally, it makes an effort to methodically define a scenario, a problem, a phenomena, a product, or a program; it also offers details on a community's living circumstances or defines attitudes towards a problem (Kumar, 2019).

There were thirty-seven (37) faculty members from the College of Arts and Sciences and College of Education at the University of Perpetual Help Molino Campus, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines as the respondents of the study. The research was done during the first semester of the Academic Year 2017-2018. A faculty training needs survey form was used as the research instrument in the gathering of data. This was in cooperation with the Office of the Director of DALTA Executive Academic, Accreditation, and Audit Committee (DEAC). It consists of four parts namely: 1) personal profile; 2) professional profile; 3) professional practice; and 4) functional competencies.

Although respondents have answered the four parts of the survey, the study only focused on the functional competencies of the teachers. Hence, there was no attempt to establish a correlational analysis between and among other variables (personal profile, professional profile, and professional practice) vis-à-vis with the functional competencies. It was the intention of the study to gather the needed data and exactly determine and appropriately address the exact training needs of the faculty members.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reveals the functional competencies of the faculty members. Research skills (r-1, l-5, f-165) are the most concerned functional competency of the teachers in which they need to continue immediate training for them to be engaged in the pursuit of it. This is followed by the marketing skills (r-2, l-3, f-85); community outreach (r-3, l-2, f-50); effective writing (r-4, l-5, f-48); classroom management (r-5, l-4, f-44); syllabus development (r-6, l-5, f-39); subject matter expertise (r-7, l-3, f-38); instructional materials development (r-8, l-4, f-35); effective instructional delivery (r-9, l-3, f-33); technology competency (r-10, l-4, f-34); and student evaluation (r-11, l-5, f-26). Based on the results, four areas of functional competencies have obtained the respective highest levels as observed by the teachers namely: research skills, effective writing, syllabus development, and student evaluation. The other seven competencies such as Marketing Skills, Community Outreach, Classroom Management, Subject Matter Expertise, Instructional Materials Development, Effective Instructional Delivery, and Technology Competency should also be given equal attention and consideration.

Table 1. Functional competencies of the faculty members

Functional Competencies	Level	Frequency	Rank
Research Skills	5	165	1
Marketing Skills	3	85	2
Community Outreach	2	50	3
Effective Writing	5	48	4
Classroom Management	4	44	5
Syllabus Development	5	39	6
Subject Matter Expertise	3	38	7
Instructional Materials Development	4	35	8
Effective Instructional Delivery	3	33	9
Technology Competency	4	34	10
Student Evaluation	5	26	11

A training needs assessment identifies the knowledge or skill gaps that exist among employees of an organization with regard to the tasks that are necessary for them to perform their employment. The process claims that the tasks that employees perform have been specified in a way that will enable the company to achieve its business objectives. As a result, by improving their knowledge and abilities in specific fields, workers will be more competent to do their tasks in part to a training needs analysis (Clarke, 2003).

Furthermore, training needs analysis (TNA) is the process through which institutions gather data to support decisions, particularly those about whether or not training may improve performance, who should receive training, and what should be covered in that training. Presenting a framework to assist practitioners in recognizing when and how organizational politics may affect such kind of assessment, with attempts to discover the specific political dimensions that impact on training decisions, may help other people to guide future research in this area (Clarke, 2003; Garavan et al., 2019).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study revealed that the 11 functional competencies have to be addressed immediately in enhancing the needs of the teachers, particularly in the University of Perpetual Help Molino Campus. This result shows that the areas of Research Skills, Effective Writing, Syllabus Development, and Student Evaluation have been improved by most of the teachers. The other seven competencies such as Marketing Skills, Community Outreach, Classroom Management, Subject Matter Expertise, Instructional Materials Development, Effective Instructional Delivery, and Technology Competency should also be given equal attention and consideration.

In like manner, professional development activities framework (PDAF) combined with school-based faculty development programs (SB-FDP) shall be initiated in the university encompassing the 11 identified functional competencies of the teachers. Hence, based on the results of the competency-based training needs assessment, a proposed faculty development activities framework is recommended for implementation in the succeeding years (Table 2).

Table 2. Proposed faculty development activities framework based on the results of the competency-based training needs assessment

Functional Competencies	Description of Current Level	Description of Next Level	Faculty Development Activities
Subject Matter Expertise	<p>Level 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applies consistent expertise in his/her field/s and effectively transfers knowledge to students • Outlines a plan for keeping up knowledge of the discipline or subject • Possesses knowledge of effective use appropriate print and electronic materials • Updates on current trends in education and information technology • Accepts feedback from students, teaching faculty, and academic administrators • Selects and attends appropriate professional development activities to enhance student learning • Considers the discipline or subject from different perspectives • Demonstrates the way(s) in which disciplines or subjects are interconnected • Supports interdisciplinary programs • Conducts objective self-observation to enhance student learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employs peer teaching on information technology • Enables learners to critically evaluate accepted practices in a field of study • Examines how modern technology has influenced the discipline or subject • Enables students who have misconceptions about a discipline or topic area to get such misconceptions addressed out • Encourages collegial, cooperative working relationships that help colleagues develop professionally • Solves issues with his/her area of expertise and educational philosophy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Effective implementation of teams; Peer teaching in general education, professional education and major / specialization subject, and aligning course content to hands-on experiences, social skills, and cultural values 2. Faculty mentoring / coaching 3. Seminar-workshop to improve theory-application content and competencies
Syllabus Development	<p>Level 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes congruence of stated learning outcomes, delivered curriculum, assessment, and supporting resources and technologies • Implements support structures for academics • Encourages collegial, cooperative working relationships that help colleagues develop professionally • Develops means to evaluate the overall academic curriculum / program • Promotes, develops, and assesses projects aimed at improving the standard of instruction • Provides leadership in the development of programs and syllabus • Strives to continuously improve instructional design • Participates in studies that examine and evaluate how teaching is done at the University as a whole 	None	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Revision of course syllabi in conformance with the recent Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Orders (CMOs) in Teacher Education and Arts and Sciences 2. Preparation of instructional materials relative to the course contents
Instructional Materials Development	<p>Level 4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determines the proper print and non-print resources to be used by reviewing the learning objectives • Assists others in developing teaching materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeks input from students, peers, and administrators through observation, discussion, or written assessments in creating and assessing instructional materials • Creates online learning resources so that students have access both inside and outside of the classroom 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seminar-workshop in using technology to develop and appraise the academic performance of students 2. Revisit the art of test construction

- Develops and publishes a professional website for a specific course for inclusion in the University's web page
- Creates instructional materials for adult learners that use technology in the classroom (graduate programs)

Effective Instructional Delivery

Level 3:

- Chooses a selection of strategies and prepares effective instructions based on the learner's developmental stage and specific requirements
- Enables flexibility in the way the lesson is delivered so that students can actively participate in achieving the stated goals
- Works creatively with students who have varying levels of motivation in the challenging social atmosphere of the classroom
- Helps students comprehend how various elements of a teaching episode are interconnected to make it easier for learning objectives to be met
- Utilizes a variety of effective teaching methods and strategies to encourage active participation from students in the teaching-learning process
- Provides students with adequate learning resources to motivate them to be interested in a lecture discussion strategy
- Modifies assignments for students and designs classroom activities to fit students' different learning capabilities and skills
- Engages a collaborative approach with peers
- Emphasizes to students that what they learn in class will prepare them for real-life
- Views each student in the class as a challenge and opportunity to become a better teacher
- Introduces to students the importance of research endeavors for effective learning
- Instills in the mind of students the wisdom of participating in outreach projects as a part of their learning process

- Provides opportunities for students to gradually establish some control over the parts of the teaching-learning process, which encourages them to take a greater role for their own learning (formulating goals, designing learning experiences, controlling the pace of teaching episodes, and devising assessment procedures)
- Promotes students' expectations while listening to their concerns and viewpoints, asking open-ended questions, and respecting their answers
- Encourages students to adopt a critical viewpoint while applying their existing knowledge and natural abilities to understand how they fit into the larger context
- Brings a fresh perspective to the classroom ensuring productivity and creative presentation of the lesson
- Encourages peers and students to work towards personal growth and deliberate educational transformation
- Guides colleagues and peers on the students' needs to be able to provide the best teaching approach
- Prepares an action plan to address questions that are identified
- Enhances the research culture by engaging in simple research activities
- Participates actively in the improvement of the quality of life of the nearby communities through various outreach programs

1. Peer teaching / Thought-showering during faculty meetings
2. Establishing professional learning groups in College of Arts and Sciences and College of Education
3. Seminar-workshop in peer teaching / team teaching
4. Seminar-workshop on the best teaching strategies
5. Seminar-workshop in using technology to develop instructional materials

Classroom Management

Level 4:

- Accepts feedback and makes use of it to develop continuously
- Freely imparts new information to other educators
- Seeks to meet and excel the community of students at the university's evolving needs and expectations

- Develops programs / policies to improve teacher-student relationships, motivation, classroom community, cooperation, autonomy, developmental growth, designing individual behavior plans, and de-escalating crisis situations

1. Development of coherence classroom environment
2. Institutionalization of growth mindset in classroom management
3. Seminar-workshop on the art and practice of classroom management

- Examines professional literature to enhance educational services
- Treats all students, teaching faculty, and other instructors with respect and civility
- Values and acknowledges the contributions of other mentoring when appropriate
- Offers possibilities for learning-teaching and encourages students to consider their own perspectives, values, and abilities to take charge of their own learning
- Examines his/her own biases or prejudices to ensure that he/she does not act on false beliefs, stereotypes, or student labels
- Builds a toolkit of techniques for supporting the unique needs of at-risk kids who display behavioural and emotional challenges and for fostering a learning environment that supports the success of all students
- Anticipates trends and proactively realigns instructional services to maximize such
- Recognizes the importance of connections and partnerships within the university community
- Demonstrates leadership as a team member inside the University community
- Seeks to enhance one's own performance within a collaborative setting
- Evaluates goals with mentors or colleagues regularly
- Promotes the creation of learning environments that value the efforts of other teachers
- Fosters the development of self-directed learners by allowing students to assume responsibility

Student Evaluation	<p>Level 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct evaluation as a crucial component of any action taken to strengthen learning outcomes • Adopts a variety of evaluation techniques according to the student group and discipline • Provides commentary on what takes place throughout the implementation phase 	None	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Professional sharing of thoughts during faculty meetings 2. Revisiting of the Zero-Based Grading System of the university
Effective Writing	<p>Level 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses a number of print approaches to effectively communicate with a wide range of audiences • Produces written communication methods that satisfy the information needs of a varied workforce that is focused on the needs of the customer • Communicates with the media in print effectively • Develops and writes modules for instructional purposes for short-term programs 	None	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seminar-workshop on module writing and revision of course syllabi based on the recent CMOs across academic programs
Research Skills	<p>Level 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous engagement in scholarly research activities • Fosters linkages with professional organizations and funding agencies • Receives research grants and funding from outside organizations on local and global levels 	None	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seminar-workshop on research proposal writing, research development, presentation, and publication 2. Seminar-workshop in the implementation of the research agenda

- Publishes research articles in prestigious publications for academia and industry
- Acts as lead proponent or project leader of research projects institutionally commissioned or externally funded
- Designs series of research agenda with commitment and dynamism
- Enhances existing research agenda with commitment and dynamism
- Sustains concerted and dedicated research efforts towards academic excellence
- Bolsters research credibility of the University with the highest ethical standards
- Achieves recognition for scholarly publications and presentations of completed full-blown research
- Contributes novel inventions, theories and the like, in favor of the good name and reputation of the University
- Upholds the academic standing of the University

Technology Competency

Level 4:

- Enables interactions with technology that are enriched by curriculum and student technology standards
- Chooses and uses the proper technology, software, and accessories for the tasks involved in teaching and learning
- Uses technology to do research, communicate through regional and international professional networks, and access information to boost professional efficiency

- Increases productivity and professional practice by using relevant and current technologies
- Examines how using technology improves learners' performance

1. Proper use of technology to improve instruction, research, and community
2. Art and practice of technology-enhanced internet relay chat (IRC)

Marketing Skills

Level 3:

- Gives ideas to improve marketing approaches
- Participates actively in the development of marketing plans of the college
- Refers new schools to be visited
- Looks for contacts who can help in marketing
- Establishes network to market the university

- Guides the recruited applicants in the admission / enrollment process
- Monitors / encourages students who have recruited new students
- Guides friends / relatives who referred new students
- Guides peers in their marketing efforts

1. Art and practice of quality marketing approaches
2. Development of marketing strategies plan of College of Arts of Sciences and College of Education

Community Outreach

Level 2:

- Joins in the community outreach programs / activities
- Attends meetings and completes tasks listed on the agenda or that are essential
- Coordinates with internal organizations
- Utilizes received grants / funds efficiently

- Communicates with external constituents
- Takes part in project planning for community development
- Uses community resources that are accessible to carry out planned activities

1. Seminar-workshop for the implementation of the agenda for community outreach programs

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